

Linking Soil Sealing and Urban Thermal Patterns through Earth Observation and Climate Modelling: A Spatiotemporal Analysis in Murcia, Spain

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Abstract: This study investigates the impact of soil sealing on the Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect in Murcia, Spain, over a ten-year period (2008–2017). By integrating the UrbClim model at 100-m resolution with the Copernicus Imperviousness Layer and SIOSE land-use data, we perform a spatiotemporal analysis of temperature dynamics across diverse urban typologies. The findings reveal that the UHI is a primarily nocturnal phenomenon driven by the high thermal inertia of artificial materials, with peak intensity occurring between 00:00 and 04:00 UTC. Statistical analysis shows that while solar radiation homogenises temperatures during daylight, substantial thermal contrasts emerge at night between heavily sealed urban and industrial zones and unsealed surroundings. Notably, the cooling influence of current urban green spaces appears limited, likely due to their fragmented nature and the grid resolution masking micro-climatic gradients. The research demonstrates that dense urban cores exhibit the highest thermal stress, suggesting that mitigation must shift towards integrated green corridors to link the city centre with the *Huerta*. These results provide a technical basis for spatial planning to enhance climate resilience in semi-arid urban environments.

Keywords: soil sealing; urban heat island; urban climate; climate adaptation; LULC.

1 Introduction

The continuous expansion of urban environments has triggered a profound transformation of the Earth's surface, characterized primarily by the replacement of natural, pervious landscapes with artificial, impervious materials. This process, known as soil sealing, fundamentally alters the surface energy balance, acting as the main driver for the Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect – a phenomenon where urban areas experience significantly higher air temperatures than their rural counterparts (Oke 1982). In the Mediterranean basin, cities like Murcia in south-eastern Spain face an exacerbated version of this challenge. The region's semi-arid climate, marked by intense solar radiation and prolonged summer droughts, intensifies the thermal storage capacity of the urban fabric, creating a critical need for high-resolution microclimatic assessments. Understanding the spatiotemporal dynamics of urban heat requires moving beyond traditional meteorological networks, which often lack the spatial density to capture intra-urban variations.

While satellite-derived Land Surface Temperature (LST) provides wide spatial coverage, it does not always correlate directly with the air temperature, which is where human

thermal comfort is determined. Furthermore, the thermal impact of soil sealing is not uniform throughout the day. Impervious surfaces, such as those found in industrial and dense residential zones, accumulate vast amounts of heat during daylight hours, which is then slowly released as long-wave radiation after sunset. This prevents nocturnal cooling and sustains thermal anomalies long after the solar input has ceased (Zhu and Woodcock 2014).

To capture these nuances, this research employs land use data from the Spanish Land Occupation Information System (SIOSE) to categorise the urban fabric (IGN, 2017) and monitor its thermal behaviour using climate data from UrbClim model (De Ridder et al. 2015). The study performs a spatiotemporal analysis from 2008 to 2017, examining temperature dynamics across six daily time windows. By quantifying the specific contribution of artificial land uses to heat retention, this work provides a technical foundation for developing evidence-based urban planning and climate adaptation strategies in semi-arid environments.

2 Materials and methods

The following subsections outline the experimental design of this study, starting with a description of the regional climate and topography, followed by the technical specifications of the datasets and the temporal partitioning used for the statistical analysis.

2.1 Study area

The research focuses on the Murcia metropolitan area, situated in the Segura River valley in south-eastern Spain (Figure 1). This area constitutes a complex Mediterranean landscape characterized by a transition from a traditional agricultural floodplain (the *Huerta*) to a rapidly densifying urban and industrial fabric. The climate is semi-arid (BSh, Köppen classification), with average annual temperatures around 18°C and extreme thermal events during the summer months. The study area's topography, being a depression (under 150 m above sea level) surrounded by mountain ranges, facilitates the development of significant thermal gradients and stationary air masses, which exacerbate the UHI effect.

2.2 Data description

The climate data were retrieved from the UrbClim model, a physics-based urban boundary layer model specifically designed to resolve urban microclimates. Unlike standard atmospheric models, UrbClim simulates the energy

Figure 1. Location of the study area in the Murcia metropolitan area (Spain). Spatial distribution of average temperature and soil sealing.

balance at the surface-atmosphere interface by explicitly coupling urban morphological characteristics—such as surface roughness, building height, and thermal inertia—with boundary layer dynamics (De Ridder et al. 2015). The model was processed by VITO under the Copernicus Climate Change Service framework, providing a continuous decadal dataset (2008–2017) at a 100-m spatial resolution.

Soil sealing data were obtained from the Copernicus Imperviousness Density layer. The 100-m resolution was chosen to ensure spatial alignment with the UrbClim temperature outputs, facilitating a direct, coherent comparison while minimising resampling-induced discrepancies. Regarding land use and land cover (LULC), data from the Spanish Land Occupation Information System (SIOSE) at a 1:25,000 scale were employed. To maintain temporal coherence with the UrbClim input data (based on 2012 land cover), the 2014 SIOSE dataset was selected. SIOSE data, generated through the integration of cadastre, agricultural records, and LiDAR with subsequent manual validation, ensures a high-fidelity characterisation of the urban fabric throughout the study period.

2.3 Methodology

The analytical framework was designed to quantify the relationship between soil sealing and air temperature through a long-term spatiotemporal assessment covering the 2008–2017 period. To capture the full diurnal and nocturnal variability of the urban thermal environment, the dataset was partitioned into six four-hour time windows: 00:00–03:59, 04:00–07:59, 08:00–11:59, 12:00–15:59, 16:00–19:59, and 20:00–23:59 UTC.

The statistical analysis involved correlating the percentage of impervious surface with the air temperature simulated by UrbClim across the entire study within these time windows. The analysis specifically targets the summer season (June to August) to identify the maximum thermal stress thresholds. This methodology ensures that the findings are both representative of the Mediterranean climate and reproducible in other urban contexts undergoing rapid densification.

3 Results

3.1 Spatiotemporal distribution and UHI intensity

The analysis of the decadal series (2008–2017) reveals a clear spatial organization of air temperature within the Murcia urban agglomeration. As shown in the Figure 1, the highest thermal values are not uniformly distributed but are strictly clustered around the most densified artificial surfaces. The urban core of Murcia and the prominent industrial areas, such as San Ginés and Polígono Oeste (SE Alcantarilla), consistently exhibit the highest air temperatures, creating a well-defined UHI.

Conversely, the traditional agricultural landscape of the *Huerta*, which surrounds the urban consolidated fabric, functions as a thermal regulator. Even under the intense solar radiation of the Mediterranean summer, these pervious and vegetated areas maintain significantly lower temperatures, providing a "cool island" effect that contrasts with the heat retention of the city. This spatial gradient is particularly sharp at the boundaries where high-density residential blocks meet the irrigation-fed plots of the Segura valley, suggesting that soil sealing, rather than regional climate trends, is the primary driver of local thermal heterogeneity.

3.2 Diurnal and seasonal variability of the soil sealing impact

The temporal segmentation into six four-hour windows provides a nuanced understanding of the UHI dynamics (Figure 2).

The analysis of the coefficients of imperviousness across the six defined time slots and four seasons reveals that the influence of soil sealing on air temperature is not constant but follows a distinct cyclical pattern. These coefficients, derived from the slopes of linear regressions, quantify the direct thermal impact of each percentage increase in soil sealing.

The results indicate that the maximum influence of impervious surfaces occurs during the nocturnal and early

Figure 2. Influence of soil sealing in temperature by seasons and time slot.

morning windows, specifically between 20:00 and 03:59 UTC, where the highest coefficients are recorded across all seasons. During these hours, the coefficients for summer and spring reach their peak values (exceeding 0.020°C per every % of sealed surface), indicating that the thermal inertia of artificial materials is the dominant driver of the local microclimate when solar radiation is absent. As the daily cycle progresses into the transition windows of 04:00–07:59 UTC and 08:00–11:59 UTC, a significant decrease in the coefficients is observed. This trend reaches its minimum during the central day window of 12:00–15:59 UTC, where the coefficients drop to their lowest levels, even showing near-zero or slightly negative values in summer. This phenomenon suggests that during the period of maximum solar intensity, the thermal contrast between sealed and unsealed surfaces is masked by the homogeneous heating of all surface types, or even by the rapid warming of dry bare soils in the peri-urban areas. Seasonally, while the nocturnal impact remains high throughout the year, the summer and spring periods exhibit the most extreme fluctuations, confirming that the thermal influence of soil sealing in Murcia is a phenomenon intrinsically linked to the nocturnal release of stored energy.

3.3 Statistical correlation and land-use impact

To identify the specific impact of urban morphology on the microclimate, the thermal distribution was disaggregated according to these main LULC categories, revealing significant differences not only in the thermal baselines but also in the variability of the recorded temperatures (Figure 3).

The high-density residential fabrics, such as the city centre and urban expansion areas, present the highest thermal medians, strictly hovering around 19.4°C, with narrow interquartile ranges that indicate a homogeneous thermal response due to their uniformly high soil sealing. In contrast, urban sprawl exhibits a much wider range of

dispersion and a significantly lower median of approximately 18.8°C, however, the substantial number of outliers suggests that while these discontinuous residential fabrics are generally cooler, their proximity to densified urban sectors can create isolated hotspots. A particularly critical finding is observed in green urban areas, which present a stable thermal median around 19.4°C with remarkably low dispersion, showing temperatures unexpectedly similar to the compact city centre. This statistical behaviour can be attributed to the limited size and low density of existing parks in Murcia, which may be insufficient to generate a robust "cool island" effect capable of countering the heat advection from the surrounding sealed environment. Furthermore, the 100-m spatial resolution of the UrbClim model may act as a technical filter, where the pixel size is unable to resolve these small-scale microclimates. Meanwhile, sectors dominated by vast impervious surfaces like industrial areas and roads show the widest thermal variability, acting as powerful but non-uniform heat reservoirs whose microclimatic impact is highly dependent on the immediate spatial context. The statistical evidence confirms that the degree of soil sealing determines the entire thermal distribution, proving that the city centre

Figure 3. Annual mean temperature by sealing LULC category.

represents the most sustained thermal stress zone, while the analysis of green spaces highlights the urgent need for larger, connected bioclimatic infrastructures that exceed current detection and impact thresholds to effectively mitigate nocturnal heat retention.

4 Discussion

The results confirm that soil sealing is the primary driver of the UHI in the metropolitan area of Murcia, with peak intensity during the 00:00–03:59 UTC window. This nocturnal dominance, driven by thermal inertia, aligns with findings in other Spanish cities such as Madrid (Carbone et al. 2024), where the heat retention of sealed surfaces has been linked to significant environmental and health stressors (Royé et al. 2021). A notable discrepancy arises in green urban areas, which exhibit temperatures similar to the city centre. However, the interpretation of green urban areas requires caution. While global studies often report significant "cool island" effects (Aram et al. 2019), the actual extent of this cooling in Murcia remains uncertain. The predominantly small and fragmented nature of the city's green patches, combined with the 100-m spatial resolution of the UrbClim model, likely leads to a "sub-pixel" averaging effect. This resolution may be insufficient to detect micro-scale "cool spots" effectively masking the localized cooling potential of urban vegetation by blending its signal with the surrounding high-temperature sealed matrix (Li et al. 2014). The findings highlight the potential for enhancing regional climate resilience by shifting from fragmented green patches toward a more integrated urban design that prioritizes soil permeability and the continuity of robust green infrastructures.

5 Conclusions

This study characterises the relationship between soil sealing and thermal behaviour within the Murcia metropolitan area, identifying the urban heat island as a primarily nocturnal phenomenon. The findings demonstrate that the coefficient of imperviousness serves as an indicator of local temperature peaks, particularly during the summer season when the nocturnal release of stored energy is most pronounced. Within this framework,

the specific cooling influence of urban green spaces may not be fully captured due to a combination of the 100-m model resolution and the inherently reduced size of these fragmented areas, which prevents the detection of micro-climatic gradients. Consequently, urban mitigation strategies should prioritise the development of continuous green corridors that link the city centre with the surrounding *Huerta*. Such integrated green axes would enhance soil permeability and facilitate the penetration of the cooling effect into the dense urban fabric. Future research, supported by high-resolution micro-scale validation, will be essential to precisely evaluate the efficiency of these nature-based solutions and their collective contribution to regional climate resilience.

6 References

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